

"Corporate Social Responsibility- An Analysis of Current Status"

Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a set of integrated programs and policies which are to be carried out with the business activities in order to make a business concern responsible for its actions and their impact on the society as a whole. In the modern business scenario the basics of corporate management has progressed drastically. Everything and everyone these days are aiming towards profitability. Every new strategy in a business is formulated with maximization of profit and prosperity in view. Organizational growth in today's world is considered to be the growth of business achieved hand in hand with the prosperity of the society around it. The traditional profit oriented selfish and egocentric individual has given way to the one who is keen to honor values like social commitment, respect for the community and its traditions and people and above all protecting the natural environment.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in reality started a new era in the basic human culture of the current corporate world. It started inculcating long forgotten human values in the society with the boardroom culture. The growing knowledge about the influence of people living around and their socio economic life can positively affect a business and its sustainability helped in bringing out the basic concept of CSR into a reality. Opening a business in a particular area in olden times meant to be providing a wide job opportunity to the people living in that particular place. Most of the other issues like loss of agricultural land, house, environmental damages etc. were ignored in almost all the cases. During those times society was always taken for granted for the progress of the business establishments. Now the situation has changed for better now. Every business has to impress the society and the people around it for its growth.

Globalization has brought a considerable change in the outlook and culture of the companies. They are no longer confined to their traditional culture. They have to accept a diversified culture and new way of social life. The people in and around its area of operation has become more educated and are more aware about everything happening around them. This socially aware as well as questioning and responding public has become really important to every single company. The theory of capitalism which always viewed business only as a profit making activity has reformed into a more civilized approach called CSR. The new generation business leaders are more concerned about the impressions of their business on the community and the ultimate

sustainability of their company through it. The growth of any large business onto the global level hastens the principle of CSR and the recognition of its benefits globally.

Fig 1- CSR – The Business & Society

Corporate Social Responsibility –Meaning

Corporate social responsibility is ‘Doing Good’ to the society in which it exists. Even though the underlying purpose of every business undertaking is profit maximization, sustainability and ultimately retention of its better side in the society. All of the above requirements of any business will be attainable only when the concern is able to impress the community and this could be done through doing some good to the society and the considering the needs of its people empathetically. Corporate Social Responsibility should be viewed by the corporates as one of the ‘best practice’ or an ‘add-on’ activity which reinforces ethics in a society and in longer run help in the well-being of both society and business as a whole.

Six core characteristics of CSR

Source: based on Crane, A., Matten, D. and Spence, L.J. 2008, *Corporate Social Responsibility: Readings and Cases in a Global Context*, London: Routledge, Chapter 1, pp. 3-20

The term CSR is closely associated with the term corporate citizenship and also shares a common platform along the concept of Triple Bottom Line (TBL). TBL mainly analyses the performance of an organization, with respect to social, economic and environmental considerations. These are the factors which are to be considered while building a sustainable business, which must also be based on a healthy economy, growing market and a supporting society.

Every healthy CSR activity should be driven out with some basic qualities like self – enlightenments, interest in philanthropic activities, commitment towards the community and the realization concerning the effect of public expectation on the business as a whole. The companies at large are expected not only to do mere business but also contribute to the economy and society. In this whole process of CSR the issues of market, workplace, environment and the society is addressed with the help of different stakeholders like shareholders, customers, media, local communities, employees, Government, NGOs etc. The following diagram explains the total structure of an effective CSR program and its effect in different areas.

Areas of Corporate Social Responsibility

Source: <http://www.bombaychamber.com/image002.jpg>

CSR in the Current Indian Scenario

India is a nation which always maintained a vision for the betterment of its society. Our *Father of the Nation* Mahatma Gandhi had a very pragmatic view regarding the social responsibility of business. His views regarding the capitalization of any company is that, accumulation of funds from the society should be considered as trusteeship of the social funds in general. He suggested that this capital which a company accumulates from the society should be considered as the trust or belief of the community on the business concern. This trust should be managed with proper responsibility and commitment towards the society in general and returned back safe to them in the form of social commitment. Today rest of the world is coming up with the idea of CSR which almost perfectly shares the same idea.

In India the development activities of the community covers a large area of sustainable development. The protection of natural environment, literacy promotion campaigns, infrastructure development programs etc. are in a much desirable state in India. Developing

economies like India needs to focus towards the disparities of income and provision of basic amenities like health services, education, water, sanitation, employment opportunities etc. To give boost to these activities the United Nations has enlisted them in their Millennium Development Goals (MDS).Corporate Roundtable on Development Strategies for the Environment and Sustainable Development – Business council for Sustainable Development (CoRE-BCSD) of India initiated by The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI), is one among such developing bodies for the CSR activities of the corporate houses. The formation of CoRE-BCSD India represents a growing realization in the Indian corporate sector of the need for a proactive and collaborative approach in working towards the goal of sustainable development.

The post liberalized and globalized Indian Economy is witnessing shrinking role of state and growing role of corporate and business sectors in overall development of the country. Corporates with their wider reach, professionalism, innovation and resources have the ability to influence the pace of growth and development. In a recent survey by TERI it was found that the public expectations from corporate and business sectors are growing. Indians feel that business sector must play a wider and more expansive societal role. In addition to providing good quality products at reasonable - prices, companies should strive to make their operations environmentally sound, adhere to high labor standards, reduce human rights abuses and mitigate poverty.

CSR Activities amongst the Budding Entrepreneurs

The culture of social responsibility can be cultivated in the forthcoming generations by encouraging them to undertake socially important projects which help the people living around them. The present academic atmosphere also provides generous importance to such live projects undertaken by the students. The knowledge which they acquire through their syllabus could be put into practice through these live projects. The practical exposure also gives them in-depth knowledge in their respective areas of academic specialization.

SIFE (Students in Free Enterprise), a live project plan under the guidance of KPMG in colleges across the globe is one such program supported by the very idea of doing something towards social uplifting through student involvement. Under this program, corporate houses, students, academicians and NGOs are all brought under a single roof in order to bring-about positive changes in the society through conducting studies and researches about the existing living conditions of economically and socially backward people and working out plans for helping

them to find out suitable solutions to end their misery. These projects aim mostly at the economic betterment of the section of the community in which they undertake activities.

Conclusion

Independent India has achieved a great deal of development in technological and information front. Still our country is lagging behind in the real economic growth. Our society is nowhere near the world average when it comes to providing basic living standards and lacks a proper blueprint of the development of our poor. The urbanization and globalizations of our markets and economy has occurred long time back, but the common man of India still stares blankly towards his future. Most of his problems are unattended and unanswered even when many NGOs address to their woes just due to the lack of sufficient funds. Although the Government brings out a great deal of social activity programs, the outreach of such programs is limited. The rich corporate houses with large economic support and employees can easily undertake such social commitments near their area of operation and can contribute a lot of positive input so as to make such programs a resounding success. Such value added projects can contribute to the growth of ethical business values and a good track record of the company's CSR. Successful companies are contributing greatly towards national wealth and overall national development and more and more should be encouraged to contribute further. Eventually a day will come in the near future when the term *socially responsible and sustainable industry* shall be recognized as the core value instead of an optional strategy for the private sector.

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